

METHODOLOGY OF ROLE-PLAYING EDUCATION OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Annotation: Present article is devoted to the role-play that is an important part in coping with a foreign language. It encourages thinking and creativity, helps students develop and practice new language and behavioural skills in a relatively no threatening setting, and can create the motivation and involvement necessary for learning process.

Keywords: communicative abilities, method of teaching, role-playing games, opportunities for real language.

English is now the most advanced language in the world. Almost all people from all over the world use it to communicate. It is because of the importance of English language in any sphere of our life. Learning a language does not just mean learning structure or vocabulary, the important thing is to understand how we use the language to communicate with this person, how we talk and what we are talking to people about.

A role-playing game is a process that has a wide range of opportunities for resilience and perception. Nowadays, teaching a foreign language is not focused on the learning process, but on how to teach students their knowledge skills easily. In addition, in the development of speech activities students need to have a good environment to increase the frequency of speech. Some learners do not know where they can play a role.

The use of role playing in speech instruction is crucial. Students can practice speaking in various social contexts and positions. According to L.S. Vygotsky [1], there is a two-way relationship between speech and gaming in role-playing. If speech emerges from the game, on the one hand, and the game itself emerges as a result of speech growth, on the other.

It is employed in a variety of settings and in a variety of methods, with simultaneous pair or group work, unstructured and unplanned, focusing on conflict scenarios of genuine relevance to the students, being the most effective in secondary school classes.

By allowing the teacher to interact and play with the students, the teacher in role affirms and encourages their participation in a make-believe scenario. It is a quick approach to create a scene and engage the students. Nowadays, there is a lot of interest in using role-playing games in English classes or foreign language lessons to simulate the actual condition of communication. Role-playing games are perfectly appropriate for a foreign language lesson. [2] Students get a true sense of reality at the same time. Students feel satisfied and happy after participating in lessons that are designed around a role-playing game. because kids will be in a welcoming and imaginative setting.

There is a requirement for communication when role-playing is used as an example of interpersonal communication. It stimulates a person's desire to engage in verbal dialogue. The demands placed on a role-playing game when teaching a foreign language to young kids shouldn't be fundamentally different. In other words, the game must encourage players to learn, spark their interest, and motivate them to complete the task successfully. Additionally, this situation is handled in regards to the situation.

Jon V. Oller thinks that role-playing increases flexibility because it improves linguistic behavior skills, which are therefore easily transferable to other contexts. [3] According to

reports, the study of philosophers sociologists and cultural historians: Gaynts Liebscher, Georg Klaus, K.G.Yusupov, V.I Istomin, V.I.Usteminko, D.Uznadze by local and foreign scholars reviewed the uniqueness of theme. A role-playing game can help improve speech activity because students are encouraged to manifest themselves when the need to say, ask, know, prove, share something with a speaker arises in itself. In addition, role-playing games are not limited to language practice, but they open the door to a wide range of opportunities for effective conduct of the lesson and allows you to use the real language. The main disadvantage of using this method in the classroom is to improve students' ability to see the world.

In a role play, each learner gets a role and is supposed to be a vital partner in speech communication. Due to the games starter acquire the following elements of contact as ability to start a conversation, keep it or interrupt the human who they are talking to if it is essential at a definite moment or agree with him or her or decline his or her opinion. Learners also develop their listening and speaking skills, their ability to ask questions. Thus, role-playing game is an innate method in teaching foreign languages.

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